

Supplementary Figure 2 – MA plots of relevant timepoints and subtelomerically expanded gene clusters.

Intramammalian refers to the mean of schistosomula and juvenile stages and sporocyst the 1, 5 and 32 day samples. Blue indicates genes which were significantly differentially expressed.